

Supplementary material for:

A model study of terraced riverbeds as novel ecosystems

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Appendix 1

Figure A1 Annual rainfall regimes

Figure A2 Empirical tradeoff relation

Figure A1. Annual rainfall regimes. (a) Averaged monthly rainfall distribution in Sde Boker, Negev desert, between 1960-2016, showing the confinement of the rainy season to six consecutive months (excluding months below 5mm). The mean annual precipitation is 93.5 mm. (b) Rainfall regime, calculated from Eq. 4, for 6 rain events, each a single day long, accumulating to $MAP = 100[\text{mm}]$.

Figure A2. Empirical tradeoff relation between specific leaf area (SLA) and specific whole-root length (SRL-w) per leaf area. The circles denote data that has been made available by Cheng et al. (2016). The red line represents a best fit to the data using Eq. (1) with $\epsilon = 3.5$.